

5th Symposium on Nutrition for the Ageing Brain

ABSTRACT BOOK

6 & 7 June **2025** | Chania, Crete (Grece)

Sponsored by:

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Foreword

The 5th Symposium on Nutrition for the Ageing Brain, held on 6–7 June 2025 in Chania, Crete (Greece), brought together leading researchers and professionals to review the growing body of evidence on how nutrients, food, and dietary patterns influence brain health throughout ageing. With a strong scientific programme and vibrant discussions, the event aimed to foster knowledge exchange and stimulate collaboration in this critical and rapidly evolving field.

The first workshop on Nutrition for the ageing Brain took place in 2014. It then grew and became a well-attended symposium, attracting up to over 100 delegates from academia, industry, and public institutions. Previous editions of the symposium have led to peer-reviewed publications in *Ageing Research Reviews*:

- *Nutrition for the Ageing Brain: Towards Evidence of an Optimal Diet* (2016 edition) - [Read here](#)
- *Nutrition for the Ageing Brain: Moving Towards Clinical Applications* (2018 edition) - [Read here](#)

The 5th edition of the symposium addressed six key themes:

- **Nutrition, Diet and Immune Function**
- **Biomarkers of Cognitive Ageing and Nutrition**
- **Nutritional Interventions for Frailty, Sarcopenia, and Cognitive Function**
- **Nutrition, Dental Health, Oral Microbiome, and Cognition:** Exploring the Connections
- **Nutrition in old age for mental health**, with a focus on brain plasticity, cognition and mood disorders
- **The Intersection of Sex, Nutrition, and Socioeconomic Inequalities**, and their implication for health in older age

In 2025, the symposium welcomed 77 participants, hosted 21 speakers from 9 countries, and received 31 abstract submissions. These numbers highlight the international interest and engagement in advancing our understanding of brain ageing through the lens of nutrition science. Most abstracts submitted were presented as posters during the symposium and are curated in the present abstract proceedings.

This event would not have been possible without the dedication and scientific leadership of the Organising Committee members, who also reviewed and rated the abstracts accepted for this edition:

- Prof. Louise Dye, University of Sheffield (UK)
- Dr. Piril Hepsomali, University of Reading (UK)
- Dr. Sandrine Thuret, King's College London (UK)
- Prof. Wim Vanden Berghe, University of Antwerp (BE)

- Dr. David Vauzour, University of East Anglia (UK)
- Dr. Nate Matusheski, Haleon (CH)
- Dr. Tomasz Rudka, Nutricia (NL)

We are grateful to all contributors—organising committee, speakers, poster presenters, and attendees—for making this edition a success. We hope this collection of abstracts will serve as a valuable resource for advancing research and collaboration in the field of nutrition and brain health.

Session I - Nutrition, diet and immune function

1) The impact of soluble and insoluble dietary fibres in zebrafish, *Danio rerio*, to LPS-induced inflammation

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A healthy and balanced whole-food, plant-based diet abundant in sources of dietary fibres (DFs) such as fruits, vegetables, legumes, seeds, and nuts exhibits putative anti-inflammatory properties. By leveraging these effects, the consumption of DFs acts as an anti-ageing dietary strategy to support the healthy ageing process. DFs can mitigate the state of chronic inflammation referred to as inflammageing by regulating and resolving acute inflammation. Our study demonstrated the in vivo impact of soluble and insoluble DFs in zebrafish, *Danio rerio*. Apple pectin, oat β -glucan, and cellulose were administered in two different percentages and feeding patterns for 12 weeks. Then, acute inflammation was induced via ingestion by exposing the zebrafish to lipopolysaccharide (LPS). We then assessed the impact of these DFs on both localized and systemic inflammation compared to the control group using 16s rRNA sequencing to explore the microbiome composition, fluorescent-based assay to quantify intestinal alkaline phosphatase, and qPCR to measure relative gene expression of pro-inflammatory markers (TNF- α , IL-1 β , IL-6, and CRP) in the blood. Additionally, we conducted tissue-specific metabolomics. Our data is expected to demonstrate the gut-modulatory impact of the DFs on the microbiome composition whilst showcasing a sex-specific and possible diet-sex interaction effect. Also, we anticipate that our results will provide insight into how the incorporation of DFs can reduce and control inflammation.

2) Blueberries, blackberries, and banana reduce metabolic endotoxemia in an intestinal Caco-2/THP-1 macrophage cell model

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Metabolic endotoxemia is a dietary lipid-induced increase in plasma lipopolysaccharides (LPS) levels that is associated with cardiometabolic and cognitive diseases. LPS in plasma can initiate a systemic inflammatory response which may contribute to neuroinflammation, a hallmark of cognitive decline. To mitigate this burden, it is imperative to identify dietary strategies to prevent metabolic endotoxemia. Consumption of blueberries, as advised in the Mediterranean-DASH Diet Intervention for Neurodegenerative Delay (MIND diet), has shown a link with reduced endotoxemia in pre-clinical studies. However, causality and the underlying molecular mechanisms are yet to be resolved. In this study, we examined the effects of in vitro digested, whole blueberries, blackberries, and bananas, on metabolic endotoxemia, and potential underlying molecular mechanisms. To this end, digested palm oil with LPS were added on the luminal site of intestinal Caco-2 cells seeded on Transwell inserts, recapitulating a high-fat absorption. Our Caco-2 cell model showed palm oil-induced LPS translocation to the basolateral compartment given that we detected significantly higher levels of basolateral LPS when Caco-2 cells were co-treated with palm oil and LPS compared to control and LPS. To examine the bioactivity of fat-induced translocated LPS, Caco-2 cell basolateral conditioned mediums were exposed to THP-1 macrophages and inflammatory NF- κ B activation in macrophages was assessed. Consistent with expectations, basolateral conditioned mediums from Caco-2 cells that had been co-treated with digested palm oil and LPS significantly induced higher activation of the NF- κ B pathway in macrophages, compared to solely palm oil. Interestingly, blueberries, blackberries, and bananas reduced the palm oil+LPS-mediated NF- κ B activation in macrophages. Furthermore, data from both transcriptomics and protein-level analyses suggest that digested fruits may induce these anti-inflammatory effects by potentially interfering with palm oil-induced LPS translocation across the Caco-2 cell monolayer, likely via transcytosis and a minor contribution of a chylomicron-mediated mechanism. In conclusion, the cognitive support of berry-rich diets could be (in part) mediated by the preventive effect on metabolic endotoxemia and warrant further mechanistic studies in humans.

3) Western Diet as a driving force of brain insulin resistance and neuroinflammation linked with AD-like changes

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¹ Nencki Institute of Experimental Biology Polish Academy of Sciences Warsaw , Poland

The Western diet (WD), originating in the USA, is characterized by ultra-processed foods rich in simple sugars, saturated fats, and cholesterol. It is a major risk factor for metabolic disorders, insulin resistance and inflammation, which drive aging. Long-term WD consumption is believed to significantly impact brain function, leading to neuroinflammation and increasing the risk of Alzheimer's disease (AD). AD is marked by amyloid- β ($A\beta$) plaque deposition and neurofibrillary tangles composed of hyperphosphorylated tau protein. There are two forms of AD: late-onset sporadic AD (SAD, >95% of cases) and early-onset familial AD (FAD, <5% of cases). Recent studies have emphasized the influence of an unhealthy diet on AD. The present study aimed to determine whether WD is a significant modifiable risk factor for neuroinflammation, cerebral insulin resistance, and AD development. In addition, the effects of WD on the mechanisms of FAD and SAD were compared. Male C57BL/6 wild-type mice (a model that can be used to simulate SAD) and Tg2576 (APP^{swe}) mice (a model of FAD) were fed WD or standard diet (CTR). The effects of WD on neuroinflammation [P2RY12, CD68, GFAP], brain insulin resistance [p-IRS-1(Ser616)], and AD traits [p-Tau(Thr231)], APP, $A\beta$] were analyzed in the entorhinal cortex (EnCx) and hippocampus (HIPP). Results indicate that EnCx is particularly vulnerable to metabolic changes in wild-type mice, showing signs of brain insulin resistance. Additionally, impaired macrophage phagocytosis and early microglial activation were observed. Disrupted p-Tau subcellular localization and decreased APP levels correlated with increased $A\beta$ labeling. In contrast, HIPP was more sensitive to inflammatory responses, as evidenced by a reduction in the microglial homeostatic marker P2RY12. In Tg2576 mice, WD primarily increased astroglial activity. Tau-related changes were present in both models, $A\beta$ plaques were detected in Tg2576 mice, and the formation and accumulation of $A\beta$ peptides was observed in wild-type mice with age. These findings indicate that WD is a key risk factor for neuroinflammation, brain insulin resistance, and AD development. This study provides novel insights into the distinct changes in the EnCx and HIPP in AD development, as well as differences between SAD and FAD models, contributing to a better understanding of AD molecular mechanisms and potential prevention strategies. Polish National Science Center grants: 2022/47/B/NZ7/03005, 2014/15/D/NZ4/04361

4) Brassica Microgreens and Vitis vinifera Extract: A Novel Plant-Food Ecosystem with Enhanced Anti-Inflammatory Properties

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Functional foods and positive nutrition promote human health by reducing the risk of inflammatory and age-related chronic diseases. Among them, microgreens are an emerging functional crop rich in valuable nutritional elements¹. Therefore, the aim of this study is to develop novel formulations of plant-food biosystems based on Brassica microgreens.

The seeds of broccoli (*Brassica oleracea var. italica L.*) are left to germinate for 2 days at 24 °C and are grown in a fully edible matrix that provides all the nutrients. The PF_{eco} has been modified with *Vitis vinifera L. (Vitis V.)* leaves extracts, obtained through Naviglio® extraction system, that are by-products of the wine industry.

After mass spectrometry and *in silico* target prediction analysis, the anti-inflammatory activity of the *Vitis V.* extract was evaluated on RAW 264.7 mouse macrophage cell line using lipopolysaccharide (LPS) as a pro-inflammatory insult, then gene expression analysis was conducted. Furthermore, we performed a human *in vitro* digestion simulation on the PF_{eco} both with and without *Vitis V.* extract. Then we tested the anti-inflammatory activity of the digestion product.

Mass spectrometry analysis of *Vitis V.* leaves extract confirmed the presence of bioactive metabolites with nutraceutical interest. Target prediction analysis revealed metalloproteinases 2 (MMP2) and 9 (MMP9) as possible targets².

Our results show that *Vitis V.* extract exerts anti-inflammatory activity by modulating the expression of pro-inflammatory cytokines.

PF_{eco} digestion product decreases pro-inflammatory cytokines and modulates the activity of MMP2 and MMP9. The protection against LPS pro-inflammatory insult is enhanced in the PF_{eco} containing *Vitis V.* extract.

In summary, this study describes the development of a fully edible plant-food ecosystem using Brassica microgreens. Incorporating *Vitis V.* extract enhanced anti-inflammatory activity without compromising plant growth, highlighting its potential as a sustainable source of anti-inflammatory bioactive compounds.

1 Florencia P. Alloggia, Roberto F. Bafumo, Daniela A. Ramirez, Marcos A. Maza, Alejandra B. Camargo, Brassicaceae microgreens: A novel and promissory source of sustainable bioactive compounds, Current Research in Food Science, Volume 6, 2023, 100480, ISSN 2665-9271

2 Suzuki T, Ohishi T, Tanabe H, Miyoshi N, Nakamura Y. Anti-Inflammatory Effects of Dietary Polyphenols through Inhibitory Activity against Metalloproteinases. *Molecules*. 2023;28(14).

5) Chicken or egg: unveiling transcription factor drivers and passengers in epigenetic age acceleration in MASLD and AD

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Background: Metabolic dysfunction-associated steatotic liver disease (MASLD) is the most common chronic liver disease worldwide. Beyond its primary impact on liver function, MAFLD/MASLD is associated with a myriad of extrahepatic manifestations, including cognitive impairment, initiating a growing interest in exploring the liver–brain axis mechanistically within MASLD pathophysiology. To better understand the pathophysiological “inflamm-aging” processes implicated in MASLD and simultaneously identify new diagnostic biomarkers (MASLD and/or AD) leveraging added value for clinical diagnosis, we examined liver biopsy DNA methylation (DNAm) changes aligning with epigenetic age acceleration (EAA) in MASLD stage progression. Finally, we evaluated generalized applicability of epigenetic EAA “inflamm-aging” biomarkers in MASLD and AD.

Results: Liver biopsies from 22 MASLD patients were analyzed using Infinium MethylationEPIC BeadChip arrays. Strikingly, progression of MASLD was characterized by gradual DNAm changes. Additionally, Horvath’s EAA significantly correlated with MASLD stage and individual histological MASLD parameters whereas LiverClock’s EAA correlated only with MASLD stage. Integrative analyses, leveraging both gradual MASLD and EAA DNAm signatures, gene expression ($n = 118$), and a MASLD-specific transcriptional regulatory network, identified (regulon-specific) transcription factor (TF) drivers and passengers implicated in MASLD and EAA progression, representing a TF-network of redox (ferroptosis), immune and metabolic/endocrine related epigenetic processes. Diagnostic applicability was further studied in biopsies and blood samples of MASLD/AD patients.

Conclusion: Gradual DNAm changes were found to align with progression of MASLD/AD and EAA, with EAA a potential non-biased quantitative biomarker for MASLD/AD. Furthermore, our integrative analysis highlights potential new therapeutic TF targets, with special emphasis on AEBP1, redox sensor NRF2 (NFE2L2) and emerging nuclear receptors including CAR(NR1I3), MR(NR3C2), GR(NR3C1), and ESRRG. While this research significantly advances our understanding of epigenetic redox-metabolic regulation of inflamm-aging responses in MASLD/AD, it also emphasizes the need for further investigations to uncover the underlying TF driver mechanisms and identify potential epigenetic reversible nutritional strategies for inflamm-aging to improve liver metabolic and cognitive functions.

6) Brassica Microgreens and Vitis vinifera Extract: A Novel Plant-Food Ecosystem with Enhanced Anti-Inflammatory Properties

Morandini¹

¹ University of Brescia Brescia, Italy

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Session II - Biomarkers of Cognitive Ageing and Nutrition: Current Advances and Future Directions

1) Western diet as a trigger for Alzheimer's disease: the role of the liver-brain axis and peripheral markers as predictors of AD development

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¹ Nencki Institute of Experimental Biology, Polish Academy of Sciences Warsaw, Poland

The **Western diet (WD)** is characterized by reliance on ultra-processed, refined foods rich in simple carbohydrates, salt, saturated fat, and cholesterol, while deficient in essential nutrients such as whole grains, fiber, and mono- and polyunsaturated fatty acids. Originating in the USA, this dietary pattern has gained global prominence, driven by lifestyle changes associated with technological advancements and a fast-paced environment. **Alzheimer's disease (AD)** presents in multiple forms, including early-onset familial AD (FAD), caused by genetic mutations in the *APP*, *PS1*, and *PS2* genes, and late-onset sporadic AD (SAD), where **lifestyle** and environmental factors play a predominant role. We explored the role of the **liver-brain axis** in AD development by assessing the effects of the WD on peripheral metabolic parameters in blood plasma and liver, as well as amyloid-beta (A β) peptide deposition in the brain. In this study, Tg2576 transgenic mice (a model of FAD harboring a mutation in the *APP* gene) and wild-type C57BL/6 mice (a model that may be used to simulate the SAD) were fed either a WD or a standard diet. Our findings revealed that WD rapidly induced metabolic syndrome, evidenced by hypercholesterolemia, insulin resistance, hyperglycemia, and elevated liver enzyme levels (ALP, ALT, AST). Notably, short-term WD consumption triggered non-alcoholic fatty liver disease, characterized by hepatic fat accumulation, immune cell infiltration, hepatocyte damage, and fibrosis in both mouse models. Additionally, WD-induced liver damage was shown to exacerbate or initiate neuropathological changes typical of AD. We identified a correlation between liver dysfunction and impaired A β clearance mechanisms in hepatocytes, leading to increased A β deposition in the liver and subsequently in the brain. Results confirm that WD-type nutrition, through its detrimental effects on liver function, significantly accelerates A β accumulation in the brain of Tg2576 mice while promoting the formation and buildup of A β peptides in neurons of C57BL/6 mice with age. This research underscores the intricate interplay between dietary patterns, liver health, and neurodegeneration, offering insights into potential preventive strategies and therapeutic interventions for AD. It also suggests that widely available, non-invasive blood tests could serve as early biomarkers to identify predispositions to age-related neurodegeneration, such as AD. Polish National Science Center: 2014/15/D/NZ4/04361.

2) Links between dietary omega-3 intake and objective and subjective cognitive performances in people aged 65-75 years.

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From age 55, one in two people reports cognitive complaints (HAS, 2014). The factors triggering these are not fully known, but their presence triples the risk of developing a mild neurocognitive disorder (MND; Liew et al., 2020). The aim of this study is to assess the link between subjective cognitive complaints and objective cognitive performance and the links between subjective or objective performances and diet, with a focus on omega-3 polyunsaturated fatty acids, promising nutrients to reduce cognitive decline (Charbit et al., 2024). 30 people (10 men and 20 women with a socio-cultural level between 2 and 4) aged between 65 and 75 years old ($\mu = 69.77$, $\sigma = 3.8$) living in Belgium took part in this study. To determine the dietary intake of omega-3 [alpha-linolenic acid (ALA), eicosapentaenoic acid (EPA), docosahexaenoic acid (DHA)], we used a specific food frequency questionnaire (Herter-Aeberli et al., 2019). We also proposed a neuropsychological evaluation (RL/RI-16, 3 matrices, tower of London, verbal fluency, etc.). Finally, we collected information on subjective cognitive complaints with a questionnaire assessing memory, language and attention/executive complaints. Concerning the complaint, the results show a negative correlation between language complaints and ALA ($r = -0.52$, $p = 0.002$), EPA ($r = -0.37$, $p = 0.021$) and total omega-3 consumption ($r = -0.51$, $p = 0.002$). A link between EPA and attentional complaints also appears ($r = -0.34$, $p = 0.035$). Total cognitive complaints are negatively correlated with ALA ($r = -0.4$, $p = 0.015$), EPA ($r = -0.43$, $p = 0.009$), DHA ($r = -0.34$, $p = 0.035$) and total omega-3 consumption ($r = -0.37$, $p = 0.021$). Concerning the objective performance, a high total omega-3 intake seems to be associated with better results in verbal episodic memory ($r_{deferred\ recall} = 0.38$, $p = 0.018$), spontaneous flexibility ($r_{semantic\ fluency} = 0.45$, $p = 0.006$) and planning ($r_{time\ for\ items\ with\ 5\ movements} = 0.36$, $p = 0.027$). Finally, we find correlations between complaints and attentional tests ($r_{3\ matrices\ result} = -0.31$, $p = 0.047$) and between memory complaints and semantic fluency ($r = -0.32$; $p = 0.041$). To conclude, dietary intake of omega-3 could play a role in the presence of cognitive complaints but also in objective performance, underlining the need for health education to prevent neurocognitive disorders.

3) Some probiotic effects on the ageing brain persist weeks after discontinuing consumption

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Modulating the gut-brain axis via probiotic supplementation has emerged as a strategy to promote healthy ageing. A small number of studies have focused on the effects of probiotic interventions on brain health in older adults, showing modest positive effects.

This exploratory pilot study is the first to assess probiotic effects after discontinuation of daily intake on brain health using self-administered questionnaires for psychological assessments and neuroimaging, targeting both structure and function of the brain. The herein reported 4-6 weeks post-intervention discontinuation follow-up was performed subsequently of assessing immediate effects of a randomised, double-blinded, placebo-controlled trial after 6-weeks intervention with two different formulations of *Lactocaseibacillus rhamnosus* HN001 (6×10^9 CFU daily).

Thirty-two community-dwelling older adults aged 68.0 ± 5.4 years, 22f/11m, were assessed at baseline, in the middle of the intervention period, immediately after the intervention period, and 4-6 weeks after discontinuing the probiotic administration; belonging to one of three groups: placebo (n=12), micro-encapsulated probiotic (n=8), non-encapsulated probiotic (n=12).

The immediate intervention effects evoked alteration in anxiety symptom scores and distinct resting state functional connectivity patterns with simultaneous changes in grey matter volume. Psychological symptom scores largely returned to baseline levels 4-6 weeks after intervention end. Levels for the Hospital Anxiety and Depression Scale (HADS) total score, its Anxiety Subscore, and the Perceived Stress Scale differed significantly between the discontinuation follow-up and immediate intervention end as well as mid-intervention, but not baseline, indicating that scores returned to baseline.

While some functional brain changes seem to persist, others were not detectable any longer, and additionally newly detected ones at discontinuation follow-up were observed. Structural brain changes did not persist.

The comparison of immediate intervention effects with discontinuation effects allows for the evaluation of transient versus sustained brain-related effects of probiotics.

All in all, some brain-related probiotic effects may indeed persist 4-6 weeks post-intervention cessation, especially on brain function level itself as indicated by resting state functional connectivity, suggesting longer lasting gut-brain axis effects than presumed, which is worth investigating more in the future.

Sponsored Session By Kyowa

1) Effect of Citicoline Supplementation on Attention in Healthy Adults: A Randomized, Double-Blind, Placebo-Controlled Clinical Trial

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Objectives

The enhancement and maintenance of brain health and cognitive function have become increasingly significant for individuals and public health organizations. In addition to the elderly, improving attention and cognitive function is crucial for middle-aged individuals seeking to lead healthy and fulfilling lives. Enhanced cognitive abilities can contribute to better performance in daily activities, work, and social interactions, thereby improving overall quality of life. Supplementation with citicoline (CDP-choline), a naturally occurring mononucleotide, has shown beneficial effects on cognitive function and behavior in populations with a wide range of impairments; however, few studies have been conducted in healthy populations. Thus, the objective of this study was to investigate the effects of Cognizin®, a citicoline supplement, on attention in healthy men and women with poor attention.

Methods

A total of 148 healthy men and women between 35 to 75 years of age with poor sustained attention participated in this randomized, double-blind, placebo-controlled trial. Participants were randomized to receive placebo (n=75) or Cognizin® (n=73; 500 mg/day) for 12 weeks. Cognitive functions were assessed at baseline and end of the intervention (12 weeks) using Computerized Mental Performance Assessment System (COMPASS, Northumbria University, Newcastle upon Tyne, UK) tasks. Safety measurements included adverse events query, hematology, and clinical chemistry.

Results

The per-protocol analysis included a total of 127 participants selected according to the planned criteria: 64 in the placebo group and 63 in the Cognizin® group. After the 12-week intervention, participants supplemented with Cognizin® showed statistically significant improvements in rapid visual information processing reaction time compared to those on placebo ($p < 0.05$). Composite scores for sustained attention reaction time and mental energy reaction time also improved to a greater extent following Cognizin® supplementation compared to placebo ($p < 0.05$). It is noted that the ITT demonstrated directional consistency. There were

no adverse events related to the study product, and hematology and clinical chemistry remained stable throughout the intervention.

Conclusions

The findings suggest that regular consumption of Cognizin® was safe, well-tolerated, and beneficial in improving sustained attention, mental energy, and rapid visual information processing in healthy males and females with poor attention.

Session III - Nutritional Interventions for Frailty, Sarcopenia, and Cognitive Function

1) Gut-brain health effects of prebiotics in older adults with suspected cognitive decline: the design of the PRECODE study

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¹ Wageningen University & Research Wageningen Netherlands

² Eindhoven University of Technology Eindhoven Netherlands

A triplication of the number of people with dementia worldwide is expected by 2050. Currently, no cure is available for Alzheimer's Disease (AD). Evidence points towards a crucial role of intestinal health as one potential etiological modifier of dementia, with the microbiota gut-brain (MGB) axis receiving increasing attention. Preclinical studies have demonstrated the benefit of dietary fibres in improving gut health and cognitive functioning. Subjective cognitive decline plus (SCD+) lies on the continuum of AD, and subjects with this condition are at increased risk of further progression. The PRECODE study is a randomised, double-blinded, placebo-controlled intervention study in 164 older adults (60-79 years) with SCD+. The study aims to investigate the effect of 26 weeks of supplementation with three different dietary fibres (chicory inulin, resistant dextrin, and seaweed polysaccharide) compared to a placebo (maltodextrin) on MGB health effects in older adults with SCD+ by assessing changes in working memory by blood oxygen level dependant signal activity and task accuracy during n-back task functional magnetic resonance imaging assessment. The secondary objectives include effects on neuropsychological test battery, other relevant brain and intestinal health parameters, and immune and metabolic parameters.

2) Exploring the neuro-differentiating and gut-modulating potential of Gamma-Oryzanol

Morandini ¹, Pucci ¹, Mac Sweeney ¹, Popescu ¹, University of Brescia Ribaudo ¹, Gianoncelli ¹, Mastinu ¹, Eleuteri ², Uberti ¹, University of Camerino Cecarini ², Abate ¹

¹ University of Brescia Brescia, Italy

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Gamma-oryzanol (ORY), a phytochemical in rice bran oil, consists of alcohol triterpenes and plant sterols, known for antioxidant and anti-inflammatory properties. Our previous research¹ suggested ORY enhances cognitive function in adult mice, modulating proteins linked to synaptic plasticity, mitochondrial metabolism, and neuroprotection.

This study explored ORY's neuro-differentiating potential using three experimental models. HPLC and mass spectrometry, identified cycloartenyl ferulate, 24-methylenecycloartanyl ferulate, campesterol ferulate, and β -sitosterol ferulates as the major components of ORY mixture. A Naviglio® system extraction method optimized gamma-oryzanol extraction from rice bran.

Then, we investigated ORY's effects on neuronal differentiation in human neuroblastoma cells and adult mouse hippocampal neural progenitor cells (NPCs). ORY stimulated neurite outgrowth in neuroblastoma cells, increasing GAP43, BDNF, and TrkB gene expression, markers of neuro-differentiation promotion. ORY directed hippocampal NPCs toward neuronal commitment. In zebrafish Tg(-3.1neurog1:GFP), ORY microinjection amplified neurog1-GFP signal and increased *islet1* and *bdnf* mRNA levels. ORY-induced *bdnf* activation was Nrf2-dependent, abolished in *nrf2a*-MO and *nrf2b*-MO zebrafish, suggesting Nrf2 involvement in ORY's neurogenic effects. Computational analysis revealed varying affinities among ORY components for Keap1-Kelch domain, with 24-methylenecycloartanyl ferulate showing promising Nrf2-inducing potential².

ORY also modulates gut barrier integrity, redox homeostasis, and inflammation. In wild-type mice ORY upregulates IL-18 expression and enhances SOD1 expression/activity, suggesting antioxidant properties.

To assess intestinal activity, *in vitro* studies using CACO-2 cells, as intestinal barrier model, were performed. Cells were treated with ORY and analyzed via Real-Time PCR. Results showed ORY modulated genes involved in gut barrier integrity, like claudins, occludin, and zonulin-1.

ORY's anti-inflammatory effects were confirmed *in vivo*. Mouse intestinal tissues were processed for RNA and protein extraction, Real-Time PCR and enzymatic assays, confirming ORY's ability to modulate pro-inflammatory gene expression and enhance antioxidant enzyme activity in the gut.

In summary, ORY is a promising therapeutic agent for neurological and gastrointestinal health, influencing the gut-brain axis. Future studies must clarify ORY's mechanisms and its components' activity.

3) Dietary flavanols rescue cerebral blood flow and shear rate during prolonged sitting in older adults

Rendeiro¹, University of Birmingham_Daniele¹, Samuel¹

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Sedentary behaviour is highly prevalent in older adults. In particular, prolonged sitting results in declines in peripheral vascular function and cerebral blood flow. Dietary flavanols, which are small polyphenolic molecules typically found in tea, cocoa and grapes, are well known for conferring benefits to the human vasculature and may be an effective strategy to counteract the impact of sitting on the cerebrovasculature.

Two acute randomized, double-blinded, cross-over, placebo-controlled studies were conducted in 40 healthy young males (high-fit: 22.2 ± 2.9 yr., N=20; low-fit: 23.2 ± 4.1 yr., N=20), and 20 healthy older adults (72.4 ± 5.0 yr). All individuals consumed either a high-flavanol (695 mg flavanols, including 150 mg (-)-epicatechin) or low-flavanol (<6 mg (-)-epicatechin) cocoa beverage just before a 2-hour uninterrupted sitting bout. Common carotid artery (CCA) retrograde and anterograde resting blood flow and shear rate, as well as arterial diameter were assessed before and after the intervention using duplex ultrasound.

Sitting significantly reduced anterograde blood flow and/or shear rate in young and older individuals ($p < 0.001$), but only resulted in increases in retrograde blood flow ($p = 0.021$) and shear rate ($p = 0.022$) in the older group. Higher levels of cardiorespiratory fitness in the young group did not protect from the effects of sitting. Flavanol intervention did not affect anterograde blood flow and shear rate during sitting in both young and older adults ($p > 0.05$), but prevented sitting-induced increases in both retrograde blood flow and shear rate in the older individuals ($p > 0.05$). Specifically, retrograde blood flow ($p = 0.028$) and shear rate ($p = 0.033$) significantly increased only after intake of the low-flavanol beverage. No changes in arterial diameter were detected due to sitting and/or flavanol intervention.

Prolonged sitting is detrimental to carotid blood flow in both young and older individuals, regardless of the levels of fitness. This seems to be more pronounced in older adults, which also experienced an additional increase in retrograde (negative) blood flow/shear rate, known to be associated with endothelial dysfunction. The current work suggests that one acute dose of cocoa flavanols may be an effective strategy to minimize the effects of short bouts of sitting on cerebral blood flow in older adults. Future studies should address whether such benefits translate into improved cognitive outcomes.

4) Targeting the gut-brain axis in ageing: the effects of 6 weeks colon-delivered multivitamin supplementation on neurocognition

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Growing evidence suggests that the gut microbiome and its metabolites, such as anti-inflammatory short-chain fatty acids (SCFAs), play a crucial role in cognitive ageing. Observational studies found that faecal SCFA levels decline with age which in turn predicted cognitive impairment in pathologically cognitive aging individuals. However, the causal relationship and underlying neurocognitive mechanisms are currently unclear. A pilot study demonstrated that colon-delivered vitamins could modify the the gut microbiome and increase faecal SCFA levels in healthy individuals, but effects in older adults and on neurocognition have not been investigated. To investigate gut-brain mechanisms involved in ageing, we examined the effect of colon-delivered multivitamin supplementation on intestinal health and functional neuroimaging outcomes in older adults. In the COMBI study (NCT05675007), a double-blind randomized placebo-controlled trial, we included 75 older adults (60-75 year) at risk of cognitive decline based on modifiable lifestyle-related risk factors. Participants consumed a colon-delivery coated capsule with vitamins B2, B3, B6, B9, C and D3, or a microcrystalline cellulose placebo capsule daily for 6 weeks. Pre- and post-intervention, participants underwent neuroimaging, faeces- and blood collection. Faecal SCFA concentrations were measured using gas chromatography. Working memory-related fMRI responses and performance were assessed with the n-back task. After adjusting for for pre-intervention values, we found no significant between-group differences in total faecal SCFAs ($p=.30$). However, post-intervention faecal levels of the SCFA hexanoic acid were significantly higher in the vitamin group compared to placebo ($p=.04$). Post-intervention neural activation in the hippocampus ($p=.01$) and right dorso-lateral prefrontal cortex (dlPFC) ($p=.02$) were both significantly higher in the vitamin group compared to placebo. However, these increases were not related to better post-intervention working memory performance ($p=.83$). Intervention-induced changes in faecal hexanoic acid levels were significantly correlated to increased dlPFC responses during working memory in the vitamin group ($\rho=0.53$; $p=.01$) and not in the placebo group ($\rho=0.09$; $p=.65$). Our findings suggest that supplementation with colon-delivered multivitamins might improve working memory-related neural recruitment of the hippocampus and dlPFC, potentially via increased levels of the SCFA hexanoic acid.

5) Promising benefits of *Phaeodactylum tricornutum* microalgae supplementation on cognitive function in healthy older adults

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Microalgae-derived bioactives offer a promising and sustainable dietary strategy to support cognitive function in aging. A *Phaeodactylum tricornutum* (Pt) extract rich in fucoxanthin and polyunsaturated fatty acids has demonstrated cognitive benefits in young adults and aging mice. This study aimed to evaluate the effects of Pt extract supplementation on cognitive function, mood, stress, and inflammation in older adults with self-perceived memory decline. Two CONSORT-compliant double-blind, randomized controlled trials were conducted. In Study 1, adults aged 55–75 received either 550 mg/day of Pt extract (4.4 mg fucoxanthin) or a placebo (PL, maltodextrin) for 24 weeks. In Study 2, participants received 1100 mg/day of Pt extract (8.8 mg fucoxanthin) or PL for 12 weeks. Cognitive performance was assessed using the COMPASS battery, evaluating memory, attention, vigilance, and executive function. Sleep, mood, stress, and inflammation markers were also analyzed. In Study 1, within-group analysis showed significant improvements in Stroop task reaction time ($p=0.005$, $d=0.81$) and delayed word recall ($p=0.010$, $d=0.53$) after 24 weeks of Pt extract supplementation, with no significant changes in PL. Additionally, hs-CRP levels decreased from 3.9 mg/L to 2.1 mg/L ($p=0.002$, $d=0.84$). In Study 2, Pt extract significantly improved ($p<0.05$) or showed trends toward improvement ($p>0.05$ to $p<0.10$) in word recall, picture recognition reaction time, Stroop color-word test, choice reaction time, and digit vigilance. Insulin sensitivity was also enhanced following 12 weeks of high-dose supplementation. These findings provide preliminary evidence supporting the cognitive benefits of Pt extract supplementation, particularly in executive function, episodic memory, vigilance, and attention. Moreover, reductions in hs-CRP and improvements in insulin sensitivity highlight potential mechanisms relevant to cognitive aging. Given the absence of adverse effects, further research is warranted to explore underlying mechanisms and the preventive role of Pt extract in cognitive decline.

6) The effectiveness of the Mediterranean-DASH Intervention for Neurodegenerative Delay (MIND) diet on cognitive health

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Mild cognitive impairment (MCI) is prevalent among older adults, with global rates ranging from 6.7% to 25.2%, and an incidence of 114.4 cases per 1,000 person-years in Hong Kong. The MIND diet, which emphasizes brain-healthy foods rich in antioxidants and omega fatty acids while limiting saturated fats, has shown promise in mitigating cognitive decline.

This pilot study evaluated the feasibility and effectiveness of a culturally adapted MIND-HK diet intervention in older Hong Kong Chinese adults with MCI and at least one metabolic risk factor. Fourteen participants (aged 75±5.4 years) from a community center were enrolled in a 12-week pre- and post-trial from June 2024 to January 2025. The intervention included four weekly in-person nutrition sessions and ongoing support via a WhatsApp group. The MIND-HK diet intervention, based on the MIND diet developed by Morris et al. (2015) and adapted from Arjmand group's 3-month intervention, was held in community centers. The intervention included four weekly in-person nutrition sessions. WhatsApp groups were used for monitoring for 12 weeks.

Primary outcomes focused on cognitive function (measured by the Hong Kong version of the Montreal Cognitive Assessment, MoCA). Secondary outcomes included lipid profile, blood glucose levels, and waist circumference. Results demonstrated significant improvements in several health metrics. The mean MoCA score increased from 16.21 to 20.79 ($p < 0.001$), indicating enhanced cognitive function. Waist circumference decreased from 87.85 cm to 83.50 cm ($p = 0.007$), suggesting reduced abdominal fat. LDL levels dropped from 2.13 to 1.49 ($p = 0.007$), and total cholesterol levels decreased from 4.09 to 3.58 ($p = 0.038$), both reflecting improved cardiovascular health. However, HDL levels slightly decreased from 1.39 to 1.31 ($p < 0.001$), and changes in triglyceride levels and blood glucose were not statistically significant. Participants reported positive feedback, noting increased knowledge about brain and heart-healthy foods and expressing intentions to continue the MIND-HK diet post-intervention. The WhatsApp group provided valuable support, enhancing adherence and allowing for personalized nutrition advice.

In conclusion, the MIND-HK diet intervention showed feasibility, safety, and preliminary effectiveness in improving cognitive function and cardiovascular health among older adults with MCI. Further research with larger sample sizes is warranted to confirm these findings.

7) A Randomised Controlled Trial To Investigate The Cognitive And Mood Effects Of Chronic Oyster Mushroom Intervention In Older Adults.

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Diet has previously been linked with cognitive health in the ageing population. Ergothioneine is a plant-derived amino acid that has previously shown benefits to cognition when administered in extract form, but it remains unclear whether dietary sources such as mushrooms can provide similar benefits. The OYSCOG study investigated the effects of a 12-week ergothioneine-rich oyster mushroom intervention on cognitive performance and mood in healthy older adults aged 60-80 years (n=80). Participants were randomised to consume four portions per week of either a dried oyster mushroom (OM) or placebo (PL) intervention. Measures of subjective mood, episodic and visuospatial memory, executive function, motor function, and serum blood samples were collected at baseline and 12-weeks post-intervention. EEG activity was recorded in a subset of participants (n=40) to examine brain activity at rest and while performing a simple n-back task. Treatment by time ANCOVA analyses, with IQ as covariate and Bonferroni-corrected pairwise comparisons, revealed significant increases in negative mood in the PL group between baseline and 12 weeks as indicated by PANAS-X mood ratings of fear and sadness and DASS-21 anxiety ratings accompanied by a slowing of switching task reaction times. For the OM group over the same period, DASS-21 anxiety ratings and RAVLT delayed recognition scores were improved, and levels of inflammatory markers (cyclo-oxygenase and nitric oxide) were reduced. After 12 weeks supplementation, treatment-related differences were evident for PANAS-X sadness, DASS-21 anxiety, and RAVLT delayed word recognition score with the OM group outperforming the PL group, displaying lower negative mood, and higher recognition scores. Overall, this 12-week intervention with OM benefited mood, memory, and inflammatory markers in older adults compared to PL, suggesting that increased mushroom intake may be beneficial in this age group. Further investigation is needed to fully understand the mechanisms underlying the observed behavioural effects which may, at least in part, be due to a reduction in inflammation.

8) The role of Intermittent fasting in promoting healthy brain ageing via the gut-brain axis in an ATG16L- δ WD spontaneous Alzheimer's disease mouse model

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Introduction

Autophagy is a critical cellular process involved in maintaining neuronal homeostasis and has been implicated in the pathogenesis of neurodegenerative diseases and associated cognitive deficits [1]. Autophagy can be upregulated by nutrient deprivation and modulates both the gut microbiota and the gut-brain axis [2]. Intermittent fasting (IF) has been shown to enhance autophagy and to improve various biomarkers of brain health [3, 4]. In this study, we evaluated the impact of IF using a 5:2 dietary regimen on cognitive decline in the ATG16L- δ WD mouse model, with a particular emphasis on the role of the gut-brain axis in mediating these effects.

Methods

Forty male 8-months old ATG16L- δ WD mice were subjected to an IF regimen (5:2 dietary schedule) for a duration of 8-months. At 16 months, metabolic parameters related to energy homeostasis were assessed, including fasting blood glucose and β -hydroxybutyrate (BHB) levels. A comprehensive behavioural analysis was conducted using the Open Field Test, Y-Maze, and Novel Object Recognition tasks. Gut microbiota composition was profiled through 16S rRNA amplicon sequencing, while metabolomic profiling was performed using ¹H NMR spectroscopy. In addition, colonic inflammatory gene expression was quantified via quantitative PCR (qPCR).

Results

ATG16L- δ WD mutant mice subjected to the IF regimen exhibited reduced overall energy intake, attenuated body weight gain, lower fasting blood glucose levels, and elevated fasting β -hydroxybutyrate concentrations compared to mice fed *ad libitum*. Notably, a significant diet effect on fasting glucose was observed only in control mice ($q = 0.0049$). A genotype-dependent effect on locomotor activity was identified, with significant differences in total distance travelled in the Open Field ($p = 0.001$). IF also led to an increased relative abundance of *Lactobacillus* and *Bifidobacterium*, in the ATG16L- δ WD mutants. Metabolomic profiling revealed that several metabolites associated with energy metabolism were differentially regulated by dietary intervention, while others were influenced by genotype, suggesting adaptive shifts in energy utilisation pathways. Preliminary transcriptomic analysis of colonic tissue indicated no significant diet-induced

changes in gene expression. However, genotype-specific effects were detected, with altered expression of claudin-3 ($p = 0.03$), NFKB1 ($p = 0.02$), and TNF α ($p = 0.049$) in mutant mice.

Conclusion

Overall, our findings underscore the intricate interplay among genotype, dietary regimen, and the gut microenvironment. IF appears to confer distinct metabolic and microbiota-related advantages that may contribute to improved gut and immune function. Notably, the physiological impact of IF is modulated by both genetic background and age, emphasising the importance of personalized nutritional strategies for metabolic and neurobiological health.

Key words: Brain ageing, neuroprotection, non-canonical autophagy, intermittent fasting, metabolism, gut-brain-axis.

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Session V - Nutrition for Mental Health in Old Age: Addressing Depression & Anxiety

1) The efficacy of prebiotic inulin-type fructans at improving mood in the context of gut-brain axis: results from two randomized human trials

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Depression and anxiety are major mental health problems affecting people worldwide, causing a significant loss of productivity in the global economy. There has been a growing interest in the scientific community to understand the interconnection between gut and brain health. Prebiotics are defined as substrate[s] that [are] selectively utilized by host microorganisms conferring a health benefit. Preclinical evidence have indicated that inulin-type fructans might have the capability to modulate stress responsiveness via the so-called gut-brain axis mechanism(s). With the purpose of translating the mechanistic evidence from preclinical studies, we hypothesized that inulin-type fructans might have a potential benefit to modulate stress responsiveness in humans. We aimed to substantiate their efficacy by conducting two randomized human trials with distinct study designs. In the first study (the SYN-ReduSTRESS Study), healthy men ($n=204$) were randomly assigned to receive 10 g/d of either oligofructose-enriched inulin (Orafti@Synergy1, BENE0) or control (maltodextrin) for 4 weeks. At the end of the intervention period, participants were subjected to the Trier Social Stress Test (TSST) considered as golden standard protocol for measuring stress responsiveness. The SYN-ReduSTRESS Study found that oligofructose-enriched inulin supplementation for 4 weeks significantly reduced anxiety ($P = 0.04$) and cortisol levels ($P = 0.002$) during the social stress paradigm (TSST). The second study (the EFFICAD Study) involved 96 healthy participants with mild-to-moderate anxiety who were randomly allocated to receive either oligofructose/OF (Orafti@P95, BENE0; 8 g/d), 2'FL (2 g/d), mixed oligofructose (8 g/d) and 2'FL (2 g/d) or maltodextrin as control (10 g/d). The results showed that both OF alone and mixed of OF and 2'FL outperformed 2'FL alone in several mood aspects (BDI-II, PANAS-SF, and STAI Y1 and Y2), compared to the control group. Following 4 weeks intervention, cortisol awakening response was also significantly reduced in OF alone ($P < 0.001$) and mixed OF and 2'FL ($P = 0.03$) groups, compared to the control group. Both studies support the efficacy of prebiotic inulin-type fructans in improving mood (depression and anxiety) and reducing stress-related hormone cortisol in the context of the gut-brain axis.

2) Effects of microalgae extract from *Tetradesmus obliquus* on gut and mental health in healthy adults with gastrointestinal complaints

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Beyond probiotics, other dietary supplements like marine natural ingredients including microalgae were identified as rich source of bioactives that could modulate the gut-brain properties and positively impact healthy ageing. Therefore, This study examined whether supplementation with microalgae extract from *Tetradesmus obliquus* Mi175.B1.a (TOME) affects gut-brain axis parameters in healthy adults with gastrointestinal complaints. A total of 34 females and 32 males with mild to moderate GI complaints were enrolled in a randomized, double-blind, placebo-controlled clinical trial. Participants were randomly allocated to receive capsules containing either 250 mg/day of TOME or a placebo for four weeks. Primary outcomes included the assessment of GI symptoms using the Gastrointestinal Symptom Rating Scale (GSRS) and Bristol Stool Scale (BSS). Secondary outcomes focused on subjective evaluation of mood, stress, and anxiety. In addition, stool, plasma, and saliva samples were collected to assess biomarkers associated with stress, sympathetic activation, intestinal permeability, and gastrointestinal health. 16S rRNA sequencing was performed to analyze changes in gut microbial populations. Daily supplementation for four weeks with TOME was safe and well tolerated in the study population. In addition, TOME significantly reduced GSRS global scores ($p=0.02$), as well as constipation ($p=0.05$) and indigestion ($p=0.03$) subcomponent scores compared to Placebo. There was also a significant increase in Shannon's index before FDR correction ($p=0.05$; FDR=0.12) and stool butyrate level was significantly lower in TOME group than in Placebo after 4 weeks of supplementation ($p= 0.039$). Both groups showed a significant reduction in perceived stress scores, but the TOME intervention group also had reduced Negative Affect scores ($p<0.001$). In addition, plasma Chromogranin A, a stress biomarker, was significantly reduced after TOME intervention ($p=0.03$). Overall, these results suggest that 4-weeks supplementation with *T. obliquus* strain Mi175.B1.a improves GI symptoms, potentially through effects on the gut microbiota, and may promote positive effects on mental health. Additional research should follow up on mental health outcomes in older population with increased stress and anxiety and investigate mechanisms underlying improvements in GI health.

3) Neuronal networking and function of the PVT MC3R neurons

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Energy homeostasis is precisely controlled by the brain. Seminal research has established the role of the melanocortin system, specifically within the hypothalamus for the maintenance of energy balance. However, when challenges to the organism are introduced, either through reduced food availability or ample food choice, the brain must regulate the response not only whether to eat or not, but how to prioritize eating behaviors. Recent work has implicated a region dorsal to the hypothalamus, the paraventricular nucleus of the thalamus (PVT) for roles in integrating internal and external environment information to elicit physiological and behavioral responses. Here we show that the melanocortin 3 receptor, (MC3R) is robustly expressed in the PVT, the region is highly innervated by POMC and AgRP neuropeptide projections and that these neurons functionally respond to different environmental perturbations – stemming from fasting or HFD feeding to early developmental overnutrition. Mapping the network of MC3R neurons using genetically tagged MC3R synaptic labeling and retrograde AAV technologies, uncovered distinct connections of the PVT to downstream targets in the amygdala and nucleus accumbens. Assessment of behavioral responses showed distinct effects mediated by PVT MC3R neuronal activity in response to feeding and influencing feeding-related behaviors (using both chemogenetic approaches and direct application of a melanocortin agonist to the PVT). The PVT MC3R neurons represent a novel nexus of behavioral control and could indicate a unique brain region involved in integrating feeding-related behavior in various challenging environments.

4) Dietary influences on symptoms and wellbeing in menopause and perimenopause

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Menopause is a natural life stage that can lead to a constellation of physical and psychological symptoms that impact on quality of life. In post-menopausal women, higher consumption of vegetables, whole grains, and unprocessed foods is associated with lower intensity of psychological symptoms, sleep disorders, and vasomotor, urogenital, and somatic symptoms. Despite a higher prevalence of psychological disturbances in peri- versus post-menopause, perimenopause is often overlooked. The current study aimed to explore the relationship between dietary nutrients and menopause symptoms, including psychological outcomes, in those experiencing menopause symptoms. Three hundred and forty-six women, who reported experiencing menopause symptoms in the past 6 months, completed the cross-sectional study. Menopause symptom severity (Menopause-Specific Quality of Life Questionnaire), depression (Centre of Epidemiological Studies Depression scale), perceived stress (Perceived Stress Scale), trait anxiety (State-Trait Anxiety Inventory), and diet (24-hour food recall) were assessed via an online survey. Demographic information included age, ethnicity, relationship status, income, education, smoking, alcohol use, BMI, and exercise. Lower protein and higher fibre predicted better vasomotor symptoms. Higher intake of vitamins and minerals predicted better psychosocial (thiamine and vitamin D), physical (magnesium, vitamins C and D), and sexual (zinc) symptoms. Negative associations were also shown for depression (selenium and thiamine), perceived stress (thiamine and vitamin D), and anxiety (selenium, thiamine, and vitamin D). This study provides evidence for beneficial associations between dietary nutrients and quality of life outcomes in women experiencing menopause symptoms. Thiamine and dietary vitamin D showed the most consistent relationships with psychological outcomes. Caution in interpreting these findings is warranted given the number of comparisons, potential for reverse causality, and limited predictive power of the nutrients. Randomised controlled trials are needed to fully understand the complex relationships between dietary components and menopause symptoms, but given the high levels of disinformation in this area further research is vital to prevent exploitation of a vulnerable population.

5) Preclinical Study to Explore Methylglyoxal-Induced Brain and Gut Changes in Anxiety and Dementia

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The rising prevalence of metabolic disorders, including obesity and diabetes, has been linked to the global increase in ultra-processed food (UPF) consumption, a major source of Advanced Glycation End-products (AGEs), including the highly reactive compound methylglyoxal (MGO). Accumulation of AGEs has been associated with chronic diseases such as diabetes, atherosclerosis, cancer, and neurodegenerative disorders. However, further research is needed to clarify their health effects, dietary levels, and potential risks.

Against this backdrop, our study explored two complementary research lines. First, we investigated whether chronic MGO treatment could induce behavioral and neurobiological alterations, leading to cognitive impairment and anxiety-like behavior. MGO-treated animals exhibited significant behavioral changes, showing anxiety-related traits and cognitive deficits. At the molecular level, we observed a reduction in glyoxalase-1 (GLO1) expression, a key enzyme in MGO metabolism. Notably, reduced GLO1 expression has been implicated in anxiety- and depression-like behavior, suggesting its role in neuropsychiatric vulnerability.

Additionally, MGO treatment induced hippocampal alterations in the pro-amyloidogenic pathway linked to Alzheimer's disease, along with increased RAGE expression, pro-inflammatory cytokines, and redox imbalance. Significant intestinal alterations were also observed, including increased MGO-glycated proteins, a pro-inflammatory state, and reduced expression and delocalization of zonulin-1 and occludin, key tight junction proteins. Microbiota analysis revealed that MGO selectively altered gut composition and metabolic pathways, with a notable increase in Lachnospiraceae and Akkermansia genera.

Considering the role of diet in influencing metabolic pathways such as GLO1 regulation, assessing the presence of food-derived AGEs, including MGO, is essential. Thus, in the second part of our study, we analyzed harmful compounds formed during food processing across different matrices. Given the rising demand for plant-based products, understanding how processing affects food safety is increasingly relevant. Using advanced analytical techniques, we examined various plant-based dairy alternatives, identifying specific potentially harmful compounds. Further research is needed to develop strategies to minimize their formation, optimizing production processes to ensure higher safety standards.